

Complexity Development of Intermediate German Learners of English: A Longitudinal Corpus Analysis

Philine Kim Tschirner (Philipps-University Marburg, Germany)

Complexity is a topic of wide range, overall separated into various levels, namely lexis (Linnarud, 1986), morphology (Brezina & Pallotti, 2019), syntax (Lee, 2004) and phraseology (Paquot, 2019). It is generally assumed that syntactical complexity of a language correlates positive with overall language competence and development. (Bulté 2008 & Paquot, Naets, Gries 2021) For example, length of T-Units, clauses per T-Unit or dependent clauses per T-Unit. (Lee 2004: 108) Previous studies already treated the topic, whereas their corpora were much smaller. (Kyle, Crossley, Verspoor, 2021). This given example also worked longitudinal and examined those students throughout years.

The present project therefore poses the following research question: How does the quantitative and qualitative linguistic complexity in written English of intermediate learners of a German high school develop between 9th and 12th grade?

To answer these research questions, the “Marburg Corpus of Intermediate Learner English” (MILE; Kreyer, 2015) gives the opportunity to analyze data of 90 students from 9th to 12th grade. Within more than 500,000 words in total, the MILE corpus for the first time gives researchers the opportunity for conducting a truly longitudinal analysis of a large number of intermediate learners of English over four years. Also, metadata such as gender and age was made available. This corpus will be analyzed using the “Tool for Automatic Analysis of Syntactic Sophistication and Complexity” (TAASSC; Kyle, 2016)

The method that will be used replicates previous studies connected to syntactic complexity (Crossley & McNamera, 2012) and is called the “bottom-up” principle, which means that data will be analyzed in the first step and will be put into bigger context in the second. The project analyses the complexity development considering Lu’s 14 parameters of measuring complexity (Lu 2010: 479).

Results are expected to show the impact of given metadata on complexity development and will be discussed in the light of their language-pedagogical. Finally, the project results in an individual and multifactorial learner curve.

References

- Brezina, Vaclaw; Pallotti, Gabriele (2019). Morphological Complexity in Written L2 Texts. *Second Language Research*. 35 (1): 99-119
- Bulté, Bram; Housen, Alex; Pierrad, Michel; Van Daele, Siska (2008). Investigating Lexical Proficiency Development over Time – The Case of Dutch-Speaking Learners of French in Brussels. *Journal of French Language Studies* 18 (3): 277-298.
- Crossley, Scott; McNamera, Danielle (2012). Predicting Second Language Writing Proficiency: The Roles of Cohesion and Linguistic Sophistication. *Journal of Research in Reading* 35 (2): 115-135.
- Kreyer, Rolf (2015). The Marburg Corpus of Intermediate Learner English (MILE). In *Learner Corpora in Language Testing and Assessment*, Marcus Callies & Sandra Götz, eds. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. 13-34.
- Kyle, K. (2016). Measuring syntactic development in L2 writing: Fine grained indices of syntactic complexity and usage-based indices of syntactic sophistication (Doctoral Dissertation)
- Lee, Jiyounjng (2004). Syntactic Complexity, Clausal Complexity, and Phrasal Complexity in L2 Writing: The Effects of Task Complexity and Task Closure. *The Journal of Asia TEFL*. South Korea: 108-124
- Linnarud, Moira (1986). *Lexis in Composition: A Performance Analysis of Swedish Learners Written English*. Malmö: C.W.K. Gleerup.
- Paquot, Magali (2019). The Phraseological Dimension in Interlanguage Complexity Research. *Second Language Research* 35 (1): 121-145.
- Paquot, Magali; Naets, Hubert; Gries, Stefan (2021). Using Syntactic Co-occurrences to Trace Phraseological Complexity Development in Learner Writing: Verb + Objekt Structures in LONGDALE. In: LeBruyn, Bert Simonne Walter; Paquot, Magali (hrsg): *Learner Corpus Research Meets Second Language Acquisition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University